

DEVELOPMENT OF SAFETY TECHNIQUE RULES TO PROTECT THE WORK OF EMPLOYEES IN LANDSCAPING

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Abstract. It is known that labor protection is a system of legal, socio-economic, organizational, technical, sanitary-hygienic, treatment-prophylactic, rehabilitation measures and tools to ensure the safety, life and health of a person in the work process, and the preservation of working ability. . Labor protection, firstly, significantly reduces the losses of the state, society and enterprises from accidents, and secondly, it ensures the health and safety of people, and it has a social effect by reducing the number of days of incapacity for work and reducing the probability of early disability pension.

Keywords: Labor protection, work, process, improvement, guidance, risk, employee.

In the organization and management of labor protection, professional selection and assessment of the professional suitability of each worker in terms of physical and mental qualities are important. Successful work in various professions depends to a large extent on a person's physical movement and mental qualities, including the work of Landscaping workers requires people to have a certain level of physical movement and mental qualities.

Based on the results of the scientific research, the damage to the members of the locomotor system of the worker in the cases related to the actions of the workers and employees of the Landscaping in the work process was studied. Based on a deep analysis of its causes, workers. Implementation of the measures and recommendations developed for the prevention and relief of injuries to street cleaners, grass cutters, tree and shrub shapers will reduce the injury rate of workers in landscaping and landscaping, and social increases protection.

Guidelines for the prevention and mitigation of the consequences of injuries to landscaping workers and employees were created, and guidelines for safety techniques were adopted for implementation in the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan.

Regarding the structure, name and text of the developed safety equipment guidelines, the following is stated in the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan of

April 30, 2023, Section 4, Chapter 20, Paragraph 2, Article 362 " For all new employees, as well as employees who are being transferred to another job, the employer must provide guidance on labor protection, safe work methods and methods, and assistance to victims of industrial accidents. must organize training.

For employees entering high-risk production or work requiring professional choice, preliminary training on safe methods and methods, occupational safety training for one month, and passing an exam and then mandatory periodical attestation on labor protection issues is conducted.

Employees of the organizations, including their leaders, are trained, guided, and have their knowledge checked by the bodies implementing the state management of labor protection in accordance with the procedures and deadlines established for the profession and types of work of these employees and leaders. must be carried out.

The employer must exclude from work persons who have not received training, guidance, and whose knowledge has not been tested in accordance with the established procedure for labor protection. Article 25 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Labor Protection", state-registered on September 22, 2016 No. 410 states that "The employer shall apply to all new employees, as well as employees It is necessary to provide instructions on labor protection for the employees, to organize training on safe methods and methods of performing work and assistance to victims of accidents.

For employees entering work in high-risk production or work requiring professional choice, preliminary training in safe methods and methods of work performance, one month internship while passing professional exams, and then on labor protection issues periodic attestation is conducted.

The employees of the organizations, including their managers, should undergo training and receive guidance on labor protection issues in accordance with the procedures and deadlines established by the state bodies implementing the state management of labor protection for their professions and types of work. , knowledge must be checked and certified.

It is prohibited to employ persons who have not been trained, instructed and whose knowledge has not been checked in accordance with the established procedure for labor protection" fully complies with the requirements and consists of a set of rules related to the following sections found

1. General rules.

1.1. The main dangerous factors in the working zone of the worker are as follows.

- 1.2. Safety requirements for used equipment.
 - 1.3. Employees must use personal protective clothing and protective equipment during work.
 - 1.4. It is not allowed to use tools and equipment that are technically unsuitable and do not meet safety requirements.
 - 1.5. Workers and employees are obliged to do the following.
 - 1.6. Workers and employees are held accountable for violating the guidelines and internal labor requirements in accordance with the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- II. Safety students before starting work.
- 2.1. Before starting work, wear the necessary protective clothing and use other personal protective equipment suitable for the job.
 - 2.2. Before starting work, blocking the workplace with barriers restricting movement depending on the level of danger, placing warning signs and providing the workplace with fire-fighting equipment.
 - 2.3. Issuance of order-permit for safe execution of work when the workplace is above 5 meters above the ground level.
 - 2.4. If a worker discovers a malfunction of the equipment before starting work, he must immediately contact his superior.
 - 2.5. Follow the safety rules in the process of refueling the working equipment if it works with fuel. Do not use an open flame when refueling. Close the cap tightly after refueling.
 - 2.6. Before starting the engine of the equipment used in the work process, move it away from the fueling area and start the engine in the operating mode.
- III. Safety requirements during work.
- IV. Safety students in the event of an accident.
- V. Safety students after work.
- 5.1. After using the necessary equipment for work, clean it and put it in the same condition as received.

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